

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PHYTOCHEMICALS, ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY AND NUTRITIONAL CONTENT OF DIFFERENT EXTRACTS FROM *PRIMULA ELATIOR*

Keywords

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ABSTRACT

Primula elatior is a medicinally and nutritionally valuable species within the Primulaceae family. In this study, comparative analyses were performed to evaluate the phytochemical composition, antioxidant activity, and nutritional content of ethanol (80%) and water extracts prepared from the aerial parts of the plant. Chemical profiles were determined using GC-MS, antioxidant potential was assessed through DPPH and ABTS radical scavenging assays, and total phenolic and flavonoid contents were quantified spectrophotometrically. In addition, macro- and micronutrient concentrations were analyzed by ICP-MS. Results showed that solvent choice markedly influenced the phytochemical composition and bioactivity. Both extracts were rich in 1,3,4,5-tetrahydroxycyclohexanecarboxylic acid, with the water extract containing a higher proportion of this compound, while the ethanol extract exhibited greater phytochemical diversity. Ethanol extract also demonstrated higher total phenolic and flavonoid contents and stronger antioxidant activity compared to the water extract. Nutrient analysis revealed high levels of calcium, potassium, and magnesium, confirming the nutritional potential of the plant. *P. elatior* presents moderate antioxidant capacity and significant nutritional value, supporting its potential as a functional food and phytotherapeutic resource. Nevertheless, the findings highlight the need for further studies focusing on in vivo bioavailability, broader pharmacological activities, and strategies to mitigate heavy metal accumulation.

INTRODUCTION

Primula elatior., a member of the Primulaceae family, is a plant with commercial and medicinal importance that is widely distributed in Europe and Asia¹. Many species belonging to the *Primula* genus are known to be widely used as medicinal plants among the general public. In particular, the leaves and roots of *P. veris* L., *P. vulgaris* Huds., and *P. elatior* (L.) Hill are used as diuretics, antispasmodics, analgesics, fever-reducing, expectorant, cough-suppressing, sedative, and insomnia-relieving properties, and are used in the treatment of the common cold, acute and chronic bronchitis^{2,3}.

Antioxidants play an important role in maintaining body homeostasis. The negative effects of free radicals in the body can lead to the development of many diseases. Additionally, the harmful effects of synthetically produced antioxidants are now better understood. Natural antioxidants found in plants can neutralize reactive oxygen species, thereby protecting the human body from oxidative stress. Phenolic compounds are primarily the molecules responsible for the antioxidant activity of plants⁴. It is known that the main active compounds in the flowers and roots of the primrose plant are bioactive compounds such as triterpenoid saponins, flavonoids, phenolic acids, and phenolic glycosides. However, there is evidence that the phenolic compounds in the plant's flowers exhibit antioxidant, antimicrobial, and cytostatic properties^{5,6}.

Moreover, *P. elatior* has recently attracted attention not only for its pharmacological but also for its nutritional potential. Studies have shown that the leaves and flowers of the plant are rich in minerals—particularly potassium, calcium, and magnesium—as well as vitamin C and other micronutrients⁷. These constituents, together with phenolic compounds, contribute to the plant's overall antioxidant capacity and thus support its potential as both a therapeutic and a functional food candidate. The long-standing traditional use of *Primula* species as expectorants in respiratory ailments such as colds and coughs has also been recognized by the European Medicines Agency⁸.

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Similarly, Tarapatsky et al. (2021) reported that phenolic compounds present in the flowers and roots of the plant exhibit not only antioxidant but also antimicrobial and cytostatic properties⁹. In this context, it becomes important to investigate not only the phytochemical and antioxidant profiles of extracts obtained with different solvents but also the nutritional composition of the plant in detail.

Many studies evaluating the antioxidant, phytochemical, and enzyme inhibition effects of *P. elatior* can be found. However, each extract obtained using different solvents may contain significant differences in phytochemical and antioxidant properties. Additionally, the phytochemical properties of different organs of the plant may vary. In this regard, studies have focused on methanol or ethanol extracts, mostly on aerial organs⁷.

In this study, 80% ethanol and water extracts were prepared from the aerial parts of *Primula elatior*, antioxidant activity, phytochemical and nutritional contents were investigated, and comparative analyses were performed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant samples and extract preparation

Commercially available dried *Primula elatior* was purchased from a local herbalist. The aerial parts were rinsed with distilled water and subsequently dried under room temperature. The dried samples were ground into powder using a grinder. Then, 10 g of powder samples were weighed and shaken at a constant speed for 24 hours with 50 ml of 80% ethanol and pure water separately. The samples filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper were concentrated under reduced pressure with a rotary evaporator at 40°C until dry. The plant material residue was then subjected to maceration with water as the solvent, filtered, and dried under vacuum to obtain the extracts¹⁰.

Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analyses

GC-MS analyses were used to determine the components and relative percentages of the extracts using GC-MS-QP2010 Ultra (Shimadzu)¹¹. Helium gas was used as the carrier gas at a constant flow rate of 1.5 ml per minute. In splitless mode, the injection volume of 1 µl was designed to be 3 per minute

between 80 and 280, and after operation, it was set to 280 °C for 8 minutes. The total operating time was 40 minutes¹². The chemical composition of the extract obtained from dried air samples was analyzed using different libraries (W10N14, W9N11.L, NIST05a.L, and wiley7n.I).

In vitro antioxidant activity

The antioxidant activity of the extracts was evaluated using DPPH and ABTS radical scavenging assays. For the DPPH method, the procedure of Eruygur et al. (2019) was followed with minor modifications¹³. Freshly prepared DPPH solution (40 µg/mL in ethanol) was mixed with plant extracts dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) in 96-well plates, giving a final volume of 200 µL per well. After incubation in the dark for 15 minutes, absorbance was recorded at 540 nm. Ascorbic acid was used as a reference standard, while DMSO served as the control. Each experiment was carried out in triplicate, and results were expressed as percentage activity with standard deviations.

For ABTS radical scavenging, the assay was performed according to the method of Re et al. (1999)¹⁴. ABTS stock solution was prepared by reacting 7 mM ABTS with 140 mM potassium persulfate and diluted with ethanol prior to analysis. The extracts were then added to this working solution, and absorbance was measured at 734 nm after reaction. Gallic acid was used as the positive control.

Determination of total phenolic content (TPC) and flavonoids (TFC)

The total phenolic content (TPC) of the extracts was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu (FC) spectrophotometric method described by Clarke et al. (2013), with slight modifications¹⁵. In this procedure, 20 µL of each extract was combined with 100 µL of freshly diluted FC reagent (1:10, v/v). After 5 minutes, 80 µL of 7.5% Na₂CO₃ solution was added, and the mixture was incubated at 25 °C for 30 minutes before measuring absorbance at 650 nm with a microplate reader.

The total flavonoid content (TFC) was analyzed following the aluminium chloride colorimetric method reported by Molan and Mahdy (2014)¹⁶. Briefly, 25 µL of extract (1 mg/mL) was mixed with 100 µL distilled water and 7 µL of 5% NaNO₂ in a 96-well plate and incubated for 15 minutes at room temperature. Subsequently, 7 µL of 10% AlCl₃ was added and

kept for 5 minutes, followed by the addition of 50 μL of 1 M Scientific ICAPQ) device to determine nutrient content (Ca, NaOH and 60 μL of distilled water. The absorbance was then Mg, K, Na, Zn, Al, S). recorded at 490 nm using a spectrophotometer.

RESULTS

Nutrient content determination of *P. elatior*

From the powdered plant sample, the specified amount was weighed into Teflon tubes using the microwave digestion system (Milestone-Ethos Easy) according to the device's defined program and subjected to digestion at a specific temperature and pressure with a 1/3 ratio of $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{HNO}_3$ mixture. The resulting fraction was then diluted to a specific concentration and analyzed using an ICP-MS (Thermo

Chemical composition

Two different extracts of *P. elatior* (water and 80% ethanol) were prepared and analysed using GC-MS. The major component in the water and ethanol extracts was identified as '1,3,4,5-tetrahydroxycyclohexanecarboxylic acid' at concentrations of 57.87% and 22.11%, respectively (Table 1).

Compounds	RT	<i>Primula elatior</i> Relative Content (%)	
		Water	%80 Ethanol
Benzene, Methyl-	1,814	nd	21,42
Ethanol, 2-butoxy- (CAS)	2,908	nd	8,11
1,2,3-Propanetriol (CAS)	3,684	nd	4,27
2,3-Dihydro-3,5-dihydroxy-6-methyl-4H-pyran-4-one	6,849	nd	0,89
Benzoic Acid	7,069	nd	0,27
1-Dodecanol (CAS)	7,632	nd	0,58
1,2-Benzenediol	7.764	31.8	nd
2,3-Dihydro-Benzofuran	8,088	nd	1,86
2-hydroxypropane-1,3-diyl diacetate	8,428	nd	1,13
Benzaldehyde, 3-hydroxy-	10,319	nd	0,62
1,3-Benzenediol, 4-ethyl- (CAS)	10.685	10.34	nd
.alpha.-D-Glucopyranoside, methyl (CAS)	14,353	nd	7,1
1,3,4,5-Tetrahydroxycyclohexanecarboxylic Acid	15,111	57.87	22,11
Megastigmatrienone 2	15,752	nd	0,54
(E)-4-(3-Hydroxyprop-1-en-1-yl)-2-methoxyphenol	17,5	nd	0,81
Myristic acid	17,721	nd	0,63
6-Hydroxy-4,4,7a-trimethyl-5,6,7,7a-tetrahydrobenzofuran-2 (4H)-one	17,982	nd	0,88
4,,7-Di(methyloxy)coumarin	18,927	nd	2,12
2-Pentadecanone, 6,10,14-trimethyl-	19,038	nd	1,27
Acetamide, 2-(Diethylamino)-N-(2,6-Dimethylphenyl)-, Monohydrochloride	20,154	nd	1,6
Pentadecanoic acid	21,106	nd	10,17
Linoelaidic acid	24,02	nd	1,42
9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol	24,113	nd	1,79
Octadecanoic Acid	24,405	nd	1,75
Pentadecane, 8-hexyl- (CAS)	26,136	nd	0,92
2-Methylpentacosane	28,866	nd	1,68
Octacosane, 2-methyl-	31,644	nd	2,52
Octadecanoic acid, 2-hydroxy-1-(hydroxymethyl)ethyl ester	31,884	nd	3,54
Total		100	100

Table 1. Chemical components of water and ethanol extracts of *P. elatior*

DPPH radical scavenging activity

In our study, when the DPPH radical scavenging activity of *P. elatior* was examined, it was determined that both water and ethanol extracts showed low DPPH activity when compared to water and ethanol extracts and ascorbic acid taken as a standard (IC₅₀: 0,9812 ± 0,2418 µg/mL). The IC₅₀ values were determined to be 575,7 ± 0,8638 µg/mL in ethanol and 735,2 ± 0,7607 µg/mL in water (Figure 1).

ABTS radical scavenging activity

When the ABTS radical scavenging activity was examined, it was found that, compared to the standard gallic acid (IC₅₀: 12.88 ± 1.998 µg/mL), the ethanol extract of *P. elatior* exhibited the highest antioxidant activity with an IC₅₀ value of 164.0 ± 0.74 µg/mL. The water extract showed a lower antioxidant activity with an IC₅₀ value of 202.6 ± 0.85 µg/mL (Figure 2).

Figure 1. DPPH radical scavenging activity of water and ethanol extracts of the *P. elatior*

Figure 2. ABTS radical scavenging activity of water and ethanol extracts of the *P. elatior*

Total phenolic and flavonoid content determination

When the total phenolic and flavonoid contents of *P. elatior* were examined, the ethanol extract was found to contain higher amounts of both compounds compared to the water extract. The total flavonoid content (TFC) of the ethanol extract was 81.25

± 0.009 mg RE/g, whereas that of the water extract was 54.08 ± 0.009 mg RE/g. Similarly, the total phenolic content (TPC) of the ethanol extract was 190.8 ± 0.019 mg GAE/g, while the water extract contained 106.5 ± 0.015 mg GAE/g (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Total phenolic and flavonoid content of *P. elatior* water and ethanol extracts

Nutrient Content of the *P. elatior*

The *P. elatior*'s nutrient content was determined using the ICP-MS method. When examining the concentrations of macro

nutrients such as Ca, K, Mg, Na, and micro nutrients such as Zn, Al, S, which are essential for the plant's development, the following table was obtained.

mg kg ⁻¹	Na	Mg	K	Ca	S	Zn	Al
<i>P. elatior</i>	72.99	418.25	2544.96	2574.43	215.25	4.60	174.22

Table 2. Selected macro- and micronutrient concentrations (mg kg⁻¹) of *P. elatior*

According to Table 2, calcium (Ca) and potassium (K) concentrations in the plant were found to be quite high. While magnesium (Mg) concentration was found to be at an adequate level, sodium (Na) concentration was found to be moderately adequate.

When evaluated in terms of micronutrients, zinc (Zn) and sulfur (S) concentrations were observed to be at appropriate levels. However, the aluminum (Al) concentration exceeding 50 mg/kg⁻¹ indicates that it is at toxic levels.

DISCUSSION

The results of the present study provide new insights into the phytochemical composition, antioxidant properties, and nutritional content of *Primula elatior* extracts. The solvent-dependent variation in phytochemical profiles and antioxidant activities observed here is consistent with previous reports on other *Primula* species and medicinal plants^{6,7}. In particular, ethanol extract exhibited higher phenolic and flavonoid contents, which is in line with earlier findings indicating that polar organic solvents such as ethanol and methanol are more effective in extracting phenolic constituents than water^{9,17}.

Our GC-MS analysis identified 1,3,4,5-tetrahydroxycyclohexanecarboxylic acid as the major compound in both extracts, though ethanol extract contained a wider diversity of secondary metabolites, including phenolic derivatives and fatty acids. The predominance of phenolic acids and flavonoids in *Primula* species has also been highlighted by Tokalov et al. (2014) and Stefanis et al. (2023), who emphasized their antioxidant and antimicrobial potential^{5,18}. Similarly, Lupitu et al. (2018) reported that ethanol-based extracts of *Primula veris* contain complex phytochemical profiles and supported these findings¹.

The antioxidant activity determined by the DPPH and ABTS assays highlights the close link between solvent type and bioactivity. Both extracts demonstrated radical scavenging ability, with the ethanol extract showing relatively stronger activity, particularly in the ABTS assay. Nevertheless, the antioxidant potential of *P. elatior* was considerably lower than that of reference antioxidants such as ascorbic acid and gallic acid. While many *Primula* species have been reported to display high antioxidant activity, these results indicate that *P. elatior* exhibits only moderate effects, suggesting interspecies variability within the genus^{1,6}.

When comparing the total phenolic content (TPC) and total flavonoid content (TFC) of *P. elatior* extracts, the ethanol extract was found to contain significantly higher levels of both compound groups than the water extract. These results indicate that ethanol is a more effective solvent for extracting phenolic and flavonoid compounds from *P. elatior*. Since ethanol can dissolve both polar and semi-polar compounds more efficiently than water, it allows for better extraction of these secondary metabolites. Previous studies have also reported high levels of phenolic and flavonoid content in the methanol and chloroform fractions of *Primula* genus plants^{21,22}. Because polar organic solvents such as ethanol and methanol are capable of dissolving both polar and semi-polar compounds, this indicated that these solvents enable more efficient extraction of these secondary metabolites.

Nutrient composition analysis has shown that *P. elatior* is a rich source of calcium, potassium, and magnesium. These results are consistent with the findings of Atikmen et al. (2018), who reported that *Primula* species generally have high mineral values regardless of cultivation conditions (soil and fertilizer differences)¹⁹. High calcium and potassium levels indicate potential nutritional benefits, particularly in terms of supporting cardiovascular and skeletal health. However, the high aluminum content detected in this study is concerning. Aluminum accumulates most in the liver and brain tissue in the body. This accumulation can lead to liver damage, loss of appetite, muscle pain, and psychosis. It is known that excess aluminum entering the body can cause memory impairment²⁰. Therefore, it appears necessary to limit consumption of this plant. Consequently, cultivation practices and environmental monitoring should be considered for the safe use of *P. elatior* for nutritional or therapeutic purposes.

Taken together, the present findings complement earlier phytochemical and pharmacological investigations of *Primula* species and underscore the importance of solvent selection in maximizing bioactive compound recovery. While the antioxidant potential of *P. elatior* extracts is moderate, their phytochemical diversity and mineral content highlight the plant's potential as a functional food and adjunct in phytotherapy. Future studies should build upon these results by conducting in vivo bioavailability assessments, evaluating additional biological activities such as antimicrobial or anti-inflammatory effects, and examining environmental factors that influence heavy metal accumulation.

CONCLUSION

In summary, this study highlights the impact of solvent choice on the phytochemical composition and antioxidant capacity of *P. elatior*. While ethanol extract demonstrated higher bioactive compound content and stronger radical scavenging activity, the overall antioxidant potential was moderate compared to standard antioxidants. The plant's rich mineral profile underscores its nutritional value, though elevated aluminum content warrants caution. Together, these findings strengthen the case for *P. elatior* as a multifunctional plant with potential applications in functional food and phytotherapy, while pointing to the need for further research on its pharmacological effects and safety profile.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interests.

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